

EUROPEAN NETWORK ON CLIMATE & HEALTH EDUCATION

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Initiative

A 'Once for Scotland' Approach to Embed Sustainable Healthcare Education in Undergraduate Medical Training

The Scottish Clinical Leadership Fellow will act as a central point of liaison between all five Scottish undergraduate medical schools.

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Executive summary

NHS Scotland has committed to delivering a net-zero health service by 2040¹. Meeting this challenge requires the health and education sectors to work together to develop a workforce capable of delivering sustainable, prevention-focused, person-centred care. As the primary pipeline for Scotland's future clinical workforce, undergraduate medical education is a critical enabler of this ambition.

To do this, Education for Sustainable Healthcare (ESH) must be embedded across all undergraduate medical curricula in a coherent and consistent manner. High quality ESH can strengthen prevention and self-management, reduce unnecessary investigations, support safer and smarter medicine usage and shorten waiting times, improving overall patient and staff experiences. However, current approaches to ESH across Scotland's medical schools remain variable².

This White Paper sets out a 'Once for Scotland' approach³ with the establishment of a Scottish Sustainable Healthcare Education Board (SSHEB), supported by a Scottish Clinical Leadership Fellow (SCLF). By working together with all Scottish medical schools, the SSHEB can establish national standards, support coherent curriculum integration, oversee faculty development, and drive robust assessment and reporting.

This approach ensures all Scottish medical graduates develop the competencies needed to practice sustainably, reduce waste, and deliver value-based care, whilst aligning with GMC^{4,5,6} and MSC⁷ guidance, the AMEE consensus statement⁸ and supporting a more resilient and equitable health service.

The SCLF post can drive initial delivery, by mapping current ESH provision across Scotland and developing a unified implementation strategy (Fig 1). Transparent annual reporting using the existing Planetary Health Report Card will provide public accountability and track progress over time⁹.

The case for change is clear:

- Sustainable healthcare improves patient experience, reduces inequalities, reduces unnecessary interventions and waste, strengthens prevention¹⁰; supports [Realistic Medicine](#)¹¹ and delivers both financial and environmental value¹².
- Benefits for the public: clearer preventative advice; value-based care; improved self-management; quicker and simpler care pathways; patient empowerment; and better health outcomes.
- Benefits for Ministers and national bodies: measurable progress toward governmental targets; more efficient use of resources; clearer national standards; and a coordinated system-wide approach across Scotland's medical schools and NHS partners.

Figure 1: The Scottish Clinical Leadership Fellow will act as a central point of liaison between all five Scottish undergraduate medical schools.

Context and rationale

Context and rationale

The World Health Organisation¹³ (WHO) and the General Medical Council (GMC) recognise the threat climate change poses to health and the safe delivery of care, signalling the need to embed sustainable practice in medical education and clinical practice to mitigate these threats (Good Medical Practice⁵; Medical Licensing Assessment Content Map¹⁴; Health Improvement Scotland & SIGN Trusted Voice position statement¹⁵). Supporting this, the GMC provided a [Sustainability Q&A document](#)⁴, which reinforces the duty of medical professionals to choose sustainable solutions. The Medical Schools Council (MSC) Education for Sustainable Healthcare (ESH) curriculum⁷ provides a framework of core concepts to support integration, assessment and faculty development. The [MSC-ESH Alliance](#), one of only four Alliances in the MSC, facilitates collaboration between all UK medical schools to integrate the ESH curriculum into undergraduate programmes.

In Scotland, the principles of [Realistic Medicine](#)¹¹ align with sustainable healthcare and encourage the transition to value-based, prevention-focused, patient-centred care. Undergraduate education is the lever to normalise that practice at scale.

The challenge

The extent to which ESH is integrated into undergraduate medical curricula varies between medical schools². Barriers, such as lack of faculty expertise, time and curricular space to develop new teaching and assessment resources¹⁶ are compounded by the lack of a national integration strategy preventing quick and unified progress.

The proposed solution: A coordinated “Once for Scotland” approach will ensure equity and efficiency and act as a world leading example of collaborative, transformative action in response to the risks posed to health by a changing climate.

Governance

To build on existing links between the five medical schools initiated through the Scottish Consortium for Sustainability in Medicine, we propose the creation of a Scottish Sustainable Healthcare Education Board (SSHEB) with representation from medical school Sustainability Leads, NHS Scotland leaders, students, and Scottish Government officials (Fig 2). The SSHEB will collaborate to support and oversee ESH curricula development, integration and reporting in Scotland.

Delivery: To support the formation and refinement of the SSHEB strategy, we propose funding of a series of [Scottish Clinical Leadership Fellows](#) (SCLF) to map existing provision in the five Scottish medical schools, and to create and implement a national ESH integration framework.

We also propose that undergraduate ESH should be explicitly included and supported in the next version of [NHS Scotland’s Climate Emergency and Sustainability Strategy 2022-2026](#)¹⁷.

Figure 2: The Scottish Sustainable Healthcare Education Board will comprise of members from academia, the health service and Scottish Government.

Why Scotland can lead

NHS Scotland has already demonstrated national system-level sustainability achievements.

- The [NHS Scotland Centre for Sustainable Delivery](#) has already transformed aspects of healthcare delivery towards greater sustainability. Of their many workstreams, one highlight is the [National Green Theatres Programme](#), which has led to the near complete halt in the use of desflurane, a powerful greenhouse gas, while maintaining patient care and reducing costs. The successes in Scotland have led to the commissioning of [Green Healthcare Scotland](#) (GHS) to support the expansion of NHS Scotland's commitment to sustainable healthcare in broader clinical domains, such as the National Green Renal and National Green Endoscopy programmes.

- The principles of [Realistic Medicine](#)¹¹, developed for Scotland, align with principles of sustainable healthcare, and have encouraged the transition towards more sustainable clinical practice.

- The [European Network on Climate and Health Education](#) (ENCHE), led from the University of Glasgow, is building expertise in supporting the integration of education on climate and health into over 50 undergraduate medical schools in 15 European countries, with the potential to reach thousands of students.

- Medical ACT (additional costs of teaching) funded Clinical Lectureships, with a specific Sustainable Medicine remit, are now in place at some of the medical schools in Scotland, promoting and supporting education on the delivery of a more sustainable healthcare service.

Current baseline in Scottish medical schools

Across Scotland's medical schools, a growing body of activity reflects the increasing recognition that the delivery of environmentally sustainable healthcare practices, which typically come with improvements in financial sustainability, are essential competencies for future clinicians. Some of this activity is captured in the [Planetary Health Report Card](#), an international student led initiative which evaluates medical school engagement with education for sustainable healthcare. While momentum is clearly building, the integration to date has largely depended on local initiative, resulting in uneven coverage and limited national coherence. Understanding this baseline is therefore critical for designing an achievable, aligned, and scalable national approach.

Student Selected Components (SSCs) and Sustainable Quality Improvement (SusQI) Projects

Several Scottish medical schools now offer sustainability-focused Student Selected Components (SSCs) and support Sustainable Quality Improvement ([SusQI](#)) projects¹⁸. This approach was developed by the Centre for Sustainable Healthcare and provide students with opportunities to explore how clinical effectiveness, resource stewardship, and environmental impact interact within real healthcare pathways. Such activities align directly with NHS Scotland's commitments to sustainable, high-value care¹⁷ and equip students with practical skills in evaluating the environmental consequences of clinical decisions.

However, because SSCs and project-based learning are optional or limited in capacity, these initiatives currently reach only a subset of each cohort. As a result, graduates leave medical school with widely varying exposure and competence in sustainability-related practice². This variability represents a structural limitation that requires more consistent, baseline integration within the core curriculum.

ACT-Funded Sustainable Medicine Posts

Several institutions have benefited from ACT-funded Sustainable Medicine Lecturers and Teaching Fellows. These roles provide essential institutional capacity for curriculum development and delivery, faculty training, and cross-school collaboration. They have acted as catalysts for innovation, enabling schools to pilot new teaching approaches, strengthen alignment with NHS Scotland climate targets, and develop strategic plans for future curriculum change.

Yet these posts differ considerably in remit, seniority, and permanence, and exist in only some schools. Reliance on temporary or locally negotiated funding creates fragility and undermines efforts to establish Scotland-wide parity of provision. A coordinated approach to staffing and long-term investment would be required to ensure benefits are sustained and equitably distributed.

Standalone Lectures, Embedded Content, and Early Assessment Pilots

Most medical schools have begun integrating sustainability concepts into existing teaching structures. This includes single lectures, case-based discussions, and modules within public health, ethics, and professionalism. In parallel, some schools have piloted formative or summative assessments to test foundational understanding of sustainable clinical practice. These developments indicate a recognition that assessment is a primary driver of learning and an essential mechanism for embedding sustainable practice as a core competency.

However, these activities remain fragmented and largely exploratory. Without shared learning outcomes, coordinated mapping across curricula, and aligned assessment standards, it is difficult to ensure that all graduates achieve the consistent minimum standard of sustainability literacy and capability required to work in a modern health service.

Planetary Health Report Card participation

Students from nearly all Scottish medical schools actively contribute to the annual Planetary Health Report Card ([PHRC](#)), an internationally recognised benchmarking initiative that evaluates the extent and quality of planetary health and sustainability teaching within medical education. Participation in this process enables schools to assess their progress systematically, identify areas for development, and compare their performance and innovation with peer institutions globally.

The model of an overarching, structured, annual quality and innovation review offers an important precedent. A similar national mechanism integrating the Planetary Health Report Card and tailored to Scotland's strategic ambitions for sustainable healthcare education, would act as a powerful driver of continuous improvement. By formalising such a review process, Scotland would not only strengthen accountability and visibility in this area but also position itself as a UK leader in embedding planetary health competencies within medical training.

Current faculty training in Scottish medical schools

Faculty development activities across Scotland are helping staff build the knowledge needed to support the integration of education for sustainable healthcare. Staff involved in undergraduate teaching can access sustainability training through a range of institutional and international learning programmes, and some providers are exploring ways to extend this support to educators who work outside the NHS. These activities are strengthening the capacity to introduce sustainability topics earlier and with greater consistency across the curriculum.

Several Scottish medical schools also engage with the international network [ENCHE](#) which supports collaborative curriculum development and will offer a new [faculty development course for clinicians](#) in 2026. Communities of practice are beginning to form within Scotland, creating further opportunities for shared learning and the coordinated development of teaching resources.

Key priorities for “Once for Scotland”

Effective integration of ESH requires a coherent and coordinated national approach. In response to this, the Scottish Consortium for Sustainability in Medical Education has identified key areas for alignment and expansion across the nation.

The Scottish Consortium for Sustainability in Medical Education acts as a strategic link between Scotland's five medical schools, fostering collaboration to embed sustainability across undergraduate medical education. To support this work, the proposed SCLF will lead a targeted programme of activity designed to deliver achievable, high impact progress. Working closely with institutional leads, the Fellow will:

Fellow responsibilities

1. Consolidate and extend existing curriculum gap analyses

The Fellow will complete the mapping work already underway across institutions and identify priority opportunities for strengthening sustainability teaching within existing curricular structures. This scoped approach ensures that the work remains achievable within the available time and capacity.

2. Coordinate shared staff development and training

Rather than re-create large-scale national programmes, the Fellow will broker collaboration between schools and connect Scottish educators with relevant international courses like those available through GCCHE, and resources such as those being developed by ENCHE. The focus will be on developing a light-touch, shared set of resources that can be adapted locally, ensuring scalability.

3. Establish an agreed national baseline for undergraduate ESH

The Fellow will facilitate consensus-building across the five schools to define a practical, measurable baseline standard for ESH learning outcomes. This baseline will serve as a foundation for future expansion, ensuring consistency without imposing unrealistic curriculum redesign within the two-year window.

4. Lead the development and sharing of core educational resources

The Fellow will curate and coordinate a repository of existing high-quality teaching materials and identify targeted areas where new resources are required. By focusing on coordination rather than full-scale content creation, this workstream will reduce duplication and strengthen quality.

5. Develop a small, high-quality shared assessment item set

The Fellow will coordinate the creation of an initial, carefully quality-assured set of assessment items aligned to the agreed baseline outcomes. This pilot set can then be expanded by schools over time, establishing a sustainable long-term model.

By adopting a “Once for Scotland” approach, this initiative will deliver a coherent, efficient, and equitable framework for sustainability education. It will reduce variability between schools, optimize resource use, and ensure that all Scottish medical students graduate with the knowledge and skills to practice medicine sustainably in the context of social, financial, and environmental challenges.

Why this matters for Scotland

For patients and their families, greener care is better care¹¹. A sustainable healthcare system that promotes health, reduces duplication and limits waste strengthens efficiency and improves outcomes. It can also cut waiting times, travel and costs for patients and NHS Scotland while lowering the environmental burden. Selecting treatments that are clinically appropriate and have a reduced environmental impact protects health while limiting emissions and waste across the system. A proactive approach that focuses on promoting health and preventing disease builds a healthier population, reduces demand on services, and contributes to long-term financial and environmental benefits.

Nationally and internationally, Scotland has an opportunity to lead. Successes from a “Once for Scotland” coordinated approach can be replicated across the UK and other nations. Through links with ENCHE and their partnership with the Global Consortium on Climate and Health Education (GCCHE), alongside our established collaboration with the World Health Organization (WHO), Scotland’s example can shape global practice by setting out a process for successful implementation, and transparent reporting for international partners.

At a time when the GMC embarks on a review of the standards, outcomes and guidance that define medical education across the UK, the work of SSHEB supported by the outputs from the SCLF, positions Scotland to contribute with credibility and influence on the national discourse around ESH.

How will we measure success?

Clear monitoring, transparent accountability and systemic evaluation of impact of the SSHEB and SCLF will be strengthened through a set of complementary reporting mechanisms. Central to this is the annual submission of the established, evidence-based Planetary Health Report Card ([PHRC](#)), already in use by the majority of Scotland’s five medical schools. The PHRC offers a consistent, comparative, and student-driven framework for tracking progress in education, research, clinical practice, and institutional sustainability.

Alongside this, we will work to embed sustainability metrics within the GMC’s quality assurance cycles, including the self-assessment questionnaire, and in time, within institutions’ internal curriculum governance. This aligns our approach with evolving GMC expectations on education for sustainable healthcare along with national standards

Together, these reporting frameworks form an integrated platform for demonstrating progress against key national and professional commitments. These include Scotland’s [Realistic Medicine](#)¹¹, [NHS Scotland’s Climate Emergency and Sustainability duties and reporting](#), the GMC sustainability duty⁵, the MSC ESH Alliance Curriculum⁷, and the SHEEB implemented baseline curriculum. They also offer a clear pathway for identifying, sharing, and promoting innovation across Scotland’s medical education community, fostering shared learning and supporting cross institutional collaboration.

Challenges

Overcrowded curricula

Medical curricula are already tightly packed, with students required to master a wide range of complex knowledge and skills. Rapid scientific and clinical developments add further pressures on curricular space. This dense medical curriculum has been identified as a key barrier to implementation of sustainable healthcare into the medical curriculum¹⁶.

However, sustainable healthcare is not a discrete 'optional' topic, it is a lens that shapes how clinical practice is delivered. In fact, sustainable healthcare is simply excellent clinical care, delivered through already embedded approaches such as realistic medicine.

This means, only minimal additional teaching is required to deliver ESH. The real task is to integrate ESH into what is already taught through an infusion approach^{2,19}. This requires applying a sustainability perspective across systems-based teaching, clinical and procedural skills, vocational skills, clinical reasoning, prescribing, and imaging. However, this integrated approach, which will develop knowledge as well as skills for practice, requires faculty to be confident and prepared to deliver ESH consistently. In addition, anecdotal evidence suggests that student demand for ESH is high, indicating that a meaningful integration would be well supported.

Staff confidence and resources

Many faculty have not received training in ESH, causing a lack of confidence that has been identified as an important barrier to faculty embedding sustainable healthcare into their teaching¹⁶, even when they understand the principles. Limited time for developing materials, along with uneven access to high-quality teaching resources, can further inhibit progress.

Therefore, two key priorities identified for the proposed SCLF are:

1. to initiate a national faculty development programme, and
2. to create a resource hub hosting a shared national repository of teaching materials, case studies, and assessment tools to deliver consistent, high-quality support for ESH delivery across Scotland.

Gaps in assessment

Even where ESH content is taught, it is not always assessed. There is currently no coordinated approach to assessing sustainability competencies within undergraduate medical education in Scotland. With the inclusion of ESH concepts in the MLA from 2026-27 onwards¹⁴, students will encounter ESH-related single-best-answer questions in the Applied Knowledge Test (AKT). To adequately prepare them, schools need to embed these questions earlier in the curriculum, however questions on these topics are rarely found in Scottish medical schools' question banks.

The MLA's Clinical and Professional Skills Assessment (CPSA) also offers opportunities to assess sustainable healthcare competencies. Although few schools globally have developed CPSA-type assessments that incorporate ESH, there is a growing body of evidence of such clinically relevant assessments²⁰. Other assessment formats that support deeper discussion and application of sustainability concepts are emerging but remain limited.

Therefore, a key priority of the proposed SCLF will be to develop training in creating ESH assessments and develop a national Scottish assessment bank containing assessments for both the AKT and CPSA components of the MLA. These will cover topics such as clinical and communication skills, sustainable prescribing, shared decision making, planetary health and nutritional and lifestyle interventions for health promotion and disease prevention. This would ensure students are prepared to apply their ESH learning in their clinical practice and provide improvements and consistency in the quality of ESH-related assessments across Scottish medical schools.

Recommendations

1. Include undergraduate education in the new Climate Emergency and Sustainability Strategy

We recommend that the Scottish Government formally endorse and support the adoption of Education for Sustainable Healthcare (ESH) across all undergraduate medical programmes by academic year 2026–27 through explicit inclusion in the new NHS Scotland Climate Emergency and Sustainability Strategy. This endorsement will align with the General Medical Council (GMC) and Medical Schools Council (MSC) ESH guidance. Such a mandate will also give medical schools the clarity and consistency they need to embed sustainability principles throughout teaching and assessment, ensuring that every graduate is prepared for the health impacts of a changing climate.

2. Introduce Annual Reporting to Drive Improvement

To support ongoing improvement, we recommend establishing an annual dashboard that reports on curriculum coverage, assessment, and developments in sustainability education. The dashboard should utilise the [Planetary Health Report Card](#) and also align with national standards. Transparent reporting will allow benchmarking across institutions and highlight areas that require focused support. Scottish medical schools and health boards should provide yearly updates on how sustainability principles are embedded in student outcomes and clinical practice. This requirement would strengthen accountability and ensure that sustainability is treated as an essential component of medical education and service delivery.

3. Create a Scottish Sustainable Healthcare Education Board (SSHEB)

To provide strategic oversight and coordination, we recommend reconfiguring the existing Scottish Consortium for Sustainability in Medical Education into a Scottish Sustainable Healthcare Education Board (SSHEB) and providing support. This board should include representation from members of the Scottish Parliament, sustainability leads from each medical school, NHS stakeholders, and student representatives. Its remit would be to set national standards, coordinate shared resources, support assessment activity and oversee evaluation and reporting. By building a national community of practice, this board would bring coherence to ESH implementation and reinforce accountability across the sector.

4. Fund a series of Scottish Clinical Leadership Fellow (SCLF) projects supporting the SSHEB

To enable delivery of the priorities outlined above, we recommend that the Scottish Government commission a series of Scottish Clinical Leadership Fellow projects aligned to the work of the Scottish Sustainable Healthcare Education Board. These projects would advance the core tasks required for national implementation, including mapping current provision, strengthening faculty development, developing shared teaching materials, and supporting assessment and reporting activity. Targeted investment in these areas would provide the capacity needed for coordinated progress across all medical schools, and ultimately across the NHS Scotland workforce.

We propose to start with a series SCLF posts for 2 years in the first instance, with the SSHEB assessing progress and requirements for further SCLF posts following the pilot phase.

Conclusion

Scotland has a unique opportunity to lead the integration of sustainable healthcare in undergraduate education. The foundations are strong: national policy momentum and successful public health initiatives both within and outwith NHS Scotland, a clear regulatory direction of travel, and growing enthusiasm among faculty. What is needed now is coherence. By adopting a coordinated Once for Scotland approach, supported through the Scottish Sustainable Healthcare Education Board and dedicated Scottish clinical leadership fellows, Scotland can replace fragmented local efforts with a unified, future-facing model of education.

This will ensure every medical graduate enters the workforce equipped with the knowledge, skills and values required to deliver high-quality, person-centred and environmentally responsible care. Annual reporting, strengthened governance, and shared resources will drive continuous improvement and accountability. Through these actions, Scotland can prepare its future clinicians for the health realities of a changing climate, as well as set a global example of health systems and education providers working together to deliver equitable and sustainable healthcare for generations to come.

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Author biographies

Professor Jon Issberner is a neuroscientist and medical educator with a long-standing commitment to sustainability in healthcare and medical education. He trained in cardiac myocyte physiology at the University of Bristol, then researched the electrophysiological basis of neuronal pathways in locomotion at Tufts University and later at the University of St Andrews. Alongside his academic work, he has held leadership roles, including serving as Dean of the Faculty of Science at St Andrews, gaining experience in governance and educational strategy. He sits on the University of St Andrews Sustainable Academic Network, contributing to strategy toward 2035 net-zero emissions. He leads the School of Medicine's sustainability agenda and chairs the Sustainability in Medicine group he established. In 2023, he founded the Consortium for Sustainability in Medical Education and now also serves as its Chair. He initiated the Scottish medical student sustainability network in 2023 and is a member of ENCHE and the Medical Schools Council Education for Sustainable Healthcare Alliance.

Professor Camille Huser completed a PhD at the University of Cambridge before undertaking cancer research at the University of Glasgow. Her career then headed in the direction of the Medical School in the same institution, working both on the undergraduate MBChB, and the postgraduate Health Professions Education MSc programme. Prof Huser is now the Deputy Head of the Undergraduate Medical School (Biosciences). Prof Huser has a long-standing interest in sustainable healthcare – she has been a member of the Universitas21 Health Sciences Group Sustainable Development Goals Initiative since 2017, which she chaired in 2024-2025. Prof Huser is a key member in the Medical Schools Council (MSC) Education for Sustainable Healthcare (ESH) Alliance, which supports the integration of the MSC-ESH curriculum in UK medical schools. Prof Huser co-chairs the European Network for Climate and Health Education (ENCHE), which promotes the integration of climate and health in undergraduate curricula across more than 50 European medical schools.

Dr Emily Stevenson is a Consultant in Public Health Medicine with NHS Tayside and a Clinical Lecturer at the University of Dundee Medical School. Medical training and foundation years were completed in Edinburgh and Fife, followed by a transition to public health medicine after work with a sustainable development charity. Academic and professional interests centre on environmental sustainability and sustainable healthcare. Dr Stevenson serves as Public Health Teaching Lead and Teaching Lead for Sustainability at the medical school. Educational leadership includes delivery of a four-week Sustainable Healthcare Student Selected Component for final-year medical students (ScotGEM and University of Dundee), based on student-led, clinically embedded projects. Dr Stevenson is currently a co-investigator on the Green Ward Toolkit, part of the Design HOPES research programme, and is a founding member of NHS Tayside's Climate Change and Environmental Sustainability Team.

Dr Morven Wilson is a Consultant Anaesthetist in NHS Highland trained across the North and West of Scotland and Australia. Alongside her clinical work she is Deputy Programme Lead for Medicine at the University of Aberdeen, where she plays a key role in curriculum development and delivery. Dr Wilson has led work to embed Sustainable Healthcare across the Undergraduate Curriculum with her colleague Dr Alison Jack, developing coherent, collaborative approaches with a range of local and national partners. Dr Wilson represents the Association of Anaesthetists on the Programme Board for Green Healthcare Scotland. She is also a member of the Medical Schools Council Education for Sustainable Health Alliance and the European Network for Climate Healthcare Education.

Dr Alison Jack is Lead of Y1 Medicine and Deputy Lead of the MBChB Programme at the University of Aberdeen and the European Network for Climate and Health Education (ENCHE) UK representative. She has a background in physiology and teaches medical science and anatomy across various programmes. Her PhD focused on complications associated with diabetes. Her academic interests include medical education, health promotion and increasing the sustainability of healthcare. She works closely with her colleague, Dr Morven Wilson, to embed a sustainable approach to delivery of care into the undergraduate medical curriculum.

Dr Nayanika (Noy) Basu is an NHS GP and lecturer based in Glasgow and Lanarkshire, with experience in UK and India. Her work focuses on health inequalities, sustainability, and planetary health. She completed medical and GP training in London and the South-east. As a Deep End GP Pioneer Scheme Fellow (2016-18) and founding member of Greener Practice Glasgow, she led the Scottish Deep End Project roundtable report on climate change and health inequalities. As faculty lead for the vertical theme of Global and Planetary Health at the University of Glasgow Medical School, she helps integrate sustainability learning across all components of the undergraduate curriculum, and coordinates the student-staff partnership for sustainability. She collaborates with professional and academic networks for climate and health at local to international level and is a keen believer in our power to create excellent, sustainable, fairer health systems - where patients, staff and communities benefit from better health for all.

Dr Lynn Wilson is the Manager of the European Network for Climate and Health Education (ENCHE). She is an academic researcher specialising in the circular economy and behaviour change and completed her PhD in Management at the Adam Smith Business School, University of Glasgow. Prior to entering academia, Dr Wilson worked within the Circular Economy team at Zero Waste Scotland and has served in nonexecutive board roles for Scottish Government arm's length public bodies. Through her environmental management consultancy practice, she has advised Members of the Scottish Parliament and Members of the European Parliament on circular economy policy and sustainability strategy.

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